

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

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ABSTRACT: Loyalty of employees in labor-intensive companies is important for the continuity of production and business continuity. This study aims to determine the effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on operational employee turnover intention at CV Cahaya Kapasindo. The population in this study were all employees of CV Cahaya Kapasindo which consisted of 180 employees. A sampling of 124 employees using a proportional stratified random sampling technique. The analytical tool used is multiple linear regression analysis which has previously been tested for validity, reliability, and classical assumption tests. The test results reveal that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant effect simultaneously on turnover intention. Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect partially on turnover intention. Organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect partially on turnover intention. Higher job satisfaction and organizational commitment will have an impact on decreasing the turnover intention of operational employees.

KEYWORDS: Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, turnover intention, operational employees.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Management (HRM) is defined as an activity that includes the withdrawal, selection, development, maintenance, and use of Human Resources (HR) to achieve both individual and organizational goals, (Mukminin et al. 2019). Employee maintenance is very important to improve the quality of the company's human resources. In other words, it is recognized that the quality of human resources is a determinant of the company's success. HR in a company, namely employees.

Employees are a determining factor for the effectiveness of the company's implementation in addition to supporting facilities and infrastructure. Therefore, companies must manage and develop human resources in a professional and planned manner. HRM in companies is very necessary because it is an acknowledgment of the importance of the organization's workforce as HR which is very important in contributing to organizational goals and using several functions and activities to ensure that HR is used effectively and fairly for the benefit of individuals, organizations, and society, (Sutrisno, 2016). As for HRM, it cannot be denied that there is still a high level of turnover intention in companies.

Turnover intention is the result of an individual's evaluation of the continuation of his relationship with the company where he works but has not manifested it in real action. Factors that influence turnover intention include individual characteristics, work environment, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. Turnover Intention indicators include thoughts of quitting, the desire to leave and the desire to find another job, (Mobley, 2011). *Turnover intention can be said to be more important to study than turnover because it is to prevent real turnover.* When employees experience turnover intention, their hearts and souls are no longer in the company. Employee turnover is an important factor in small business profits. Changing employees can impact productivity, expenses, and overall business performance, (Ratmawati et al., 2020). *High turnover intention can indicate that the company is ineffective, reduces efficiency and productivity so that it can harm the company, in the end the company loses employees who already have previous experience and needs to train new employees,* (Joarder et al., 2011).

Job satisfaction is when there is no difference between what is desired and the perception of reality, because the desired minimum limit has been met. Indicators of employee job satisfaction include the work itself, rewards, promotion opportunities, supervision, and co-workers, (Indrasari, 2017). Job satisfaction is one of the things that must be considered by the company because it can affect employee loyalty and employees are valuable assets that must be maintained so that they will provide high work productivity for the company. Therefore, companies must be able to fulfill job satisfaction and increase positive organizational commitment in order to minimize employee turnover rates. This job satisfaction is the result of an assessment that causes a person to achieve the value of his work or fulfill his basic needs and helps in determining the extent to which a person likes or dislikes his work.

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

Organizational commitment is the degree to which a person knows the company and its goals. Organizational commitment indicators consist of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment, (Kreitner dan Kinicki, 2014). High organizational commitment will reduce the desire to change jobs of its employees, (Halimsetiono, 2014). Organizational commitment is a belief that binds an individual or employee with an organization as indicated by an attitude of loyalty, a sense of involvement with tasks, his belief in the values and goals of the organization, where high commitment is indicated by a low level of absenteeism and a low level of turnover. individual or employee, (Ningrum et al., 2021). In carrying out his work, an employee has a very basic problem where employees will not have the same level of commitment. Specific characteristics of the job can increase the sense of responsibility and a sense of attachment to the organization. The higher the employee's commitment to the company, the better the loyalty and desire to survive in various conditions so that the effectiveness of achieving company goals can run optimally.

CV Cahaya Kapisindo was founded in Bogor in 2003. This company is engaged in manufacturing children's toys, especially dolls. CV Cahaya Kapisindo specializes in the production of dolls aimed at all levels of society. The emphasis on local products is color, shape, and trends. Before this company was established, the director had founded a company called PT Dream Toys which was founded in Sukabumi, engaged in the same field but specializing in export production to various European regions. PT Dream Toys did not last long, due to the behavior of its employees who experienced indications of turnover intention which led to turnover, so that the company suffered considerable losses and resulted in business closing. This condition has become the impetus for the management of CV Cahaya Kapisindo to improve and enhance its HRM.

Along with the company's journey that has been up and down many times, it is undeniable that there are challenges and problems that have arisen. The problem of work routines and the various obligations imposed on each employee has different variations and versions for everyone. This problem will eventually develop into a complex problem that affects all aspects of the company. The problem that arises is caused by an indication of employee turnover intention, causing employees to be undisciplined at work. Turnover data for the 2021 period at CV Cahaya Kapisindo is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. CV Cahaya Kapisindo Employee Turnover Data for the 2021 Period

Month	Number of employee (person)	of Employee leaving (person)	Employee coming (person)	Number of employee (person)	Turnover (%)
January	138	4	13	147	3
February	147	2	1	146	1
March	146	0	0	146	0
April	146	0	0	146	0
May	146	12	1	135	8
June	135	11	1	123	7
July	123	7	9	125	5
August	125	2	9	132	1
September	132	3	54	183	2
October	183	7	0	176	5
November	176	4	8	180	3
December	180	1	0	179	1
Average	148	4	8	152	3

Source: CV Cahaya Kapisindo, 2022

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that in the 2021 period, the average employee turnover is 3% per year. This is not in line with (Ratmawati et al., 2020) that the ideal turnover is 10% in a year. This means that if the turnover percentage is more than 10% it is said to be high. High turnover can cause losses both financially and morally to companies and employees who are still working. From these data it can be concluded that the employee turnover data for the 2021 period is not high. However, this study emphasizes the intention of employees to leave the company, so a pre-survey research was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 30 respondents to CV Cahaya Kapisindo's employee turnover intention, which can be concluded that the average employee turnover intention of CV Cahaya Kapisindo is very high, namely by 73%. Based on the results of the Pre-Survey, it is necessary to conduct research on the factors that cause high employee turnover intention at CV Cahaya Kapisindo. So that in this case the factors that influence turnover intention at CV Cahaya Kapisindo are job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Based on the results of the pre-survey, the level of employee satisfaction is low at 40%, because the salary received does not match the workload and is not balanced with other employees. The compensation data for CV Cahaya Kapisindo shows that not all employees in several divisions receive a basic salary according to the UMK. The basic salary of CV Cahaya Kapisindo employees is adjusted to the performance and abilities of employees based on the manager's assessment, so it can be concluded that employees in several work sections do not get a balanced or equal basic salary. A balanced base salary is obtained for the

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

managerial and warehouse staff, packing, mechanics, quality control, and mold sections. BPJS Health is given to all employees in stages, but until now the press, laser, sample, cutting, sewing, finishing, stuffing, and driver sections have not received BPJS Health from the company. BPJS TK (Employment) will also be given to several work sections in stages for employees who have not received such as press, laser, cutting, sewing and finishing sections, but BPJS TK will not be given to employees in the packing, cleaning and cotton sections. Types of bonus compensation, BPJS TK, paid leave, and lunches are obtained by employees not in full or only in some parts of work. From the reward data it can be concluded that compensation has not been evenly received by employees, meaning that there is discrimination between companies against employees of CV Cahaya Kapasindo. Low employee job satisfaction can result in low employee performance which causes errors in production. Production errors that pass quality control can cause sales returns. Sales returns are goods returned by the customer and given a sales discount given or exchange of the goods for factors such as damage to the goods that occurred during shipping, goods that were defective after being sold and after being produced or the type of goods that are not correct, (Skousen et al., 2009).

The average sales return at CV Cahaya Kapasindo per year is 2.39% due to wrong stitches, dirty materials due to production and shipping errors, and torn fabrics due to tailor inaccuracies. Solutions for sales returns include re-production by replacing the entire product that is faulty because it cannot be repaired, replacing some parts of the product that are faulty that can no longer be repaired, or disassembling the cotton and then washing the cloth.

Another factor that influences turnover intention is organizational commitment. High commitment is shown by low levels of absenteeism, (Ningrum et al., 2021). Based on the attendance data obtained, it shows that the absenteeism rate for CV Cahaya Kapasindo employees is quite high, with an annual average of 5%. This means that organizational commitment at CV Cahaya Kapasindo is low. The absentee level that occurred at CV Cahaya Kapasindo is considered to have exceeded the tolerance limit set by the company at 2%. This high employee absenteeism is allegedly due to low employee organizational commitment to the company. The results of the pre-survey showed that the average percentage of organizational commitment possessed by employees at CV Cahaya Kapasindo was low at 37%. This can be seen in the low interpretation of the continuance commitment indicator, where as many as 26.6% of employees feel it is a loss if they leave the company by considering economic value and other risks.

II. METHOD

This research uses descriptive and verification methods with a quantitative analysis approach. The population in this study were all employees totaling 180 employees with a sample of 124 employees using a proportional stratified random sampling technique with the Slovin formula, an error margin of 5%.

The variables in this study consist of two types, namely the independent variable consisting of job satisfaction and organizational commitment, the dependent variable namely turnover intention. Job satisfaction is measured through the work itself, rewards, promotions, supervision, and colleagues. Organizational commitment is measured through affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment. Furthermore, turnover intention is measured based on the thought of quitting, the desire to leave, and the desire to find another job. All statements contained in the questionnaire were measured using a Likert scale with five points ranging from 1 for the strongly disagree category to 5 for strongly agree.

This study uses primary data obtained directly through observation, interviews, and questionnaires given to respondents, and secondary data obtained from company archive data and other literature. The data analysis tool used in this study used multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the Statistical Package For Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Before testing the relationship between variables, validity and reliability tests were carried out as well as classical assumption tests.

The results of the first validity test on the variable job satisfaction (X1) as measured by 17 statement items indicate that 2 of the statement items on the questionnaire in this study are invalid, while the rest are valid. This is indicated by the rcount value of the 2 statement items being smaller than rtable (0.3) meaning that it is declared invalid, while the remaining rcount is greater than rtable (0.3) meaning that some of the statement items on the job satisfaction variable (X1) are declared valid. Based on this, data processing is repeated by removing invalid statement items so that the statement of job satisfaction (X1) becomes 15 statement items. Re-processing of data shows that the questionnaire items in the second validity test on job satisfaction variables are valid. This is indicated by the value of rcount for each item that is greater than rtable (0.3) meaning that all items in the statement of the variable job satisfaction (X1) are declared valid.

The results of the first validity test of the organizational commitment variable (X2) as measured by 8 statement items indicate that 1 statement item on the questionnaire in this study was declared invalid because rcount 0.068 is smaller than rtable 0.3 ($0.068 < 0.3$), while statement items others in the organizational commitment variable are declared valid as indicated by the rcount value for each item that is greater than rtable (0.3) meaning that some of the organizational commitment variable questions (X2) are declared valid. Based on this, data processing is repeated by removing invalid statement items so that the organizational commitment statement items (X2) become 7 statement items. Re-processing of data on the organizational commitment variable shows that the questionnaire items in the second validity test are valid. This is indicated by the rcount value for each item that is

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

greater than the rtable (0.3) meaning that all items in the organizational commitment variable statement (X2) are declared valid. Hasil uji validitas *turnover intention* menunjukkan bahwa butir-butir kuesioner dalam penelitian ini adalah valid. Hal ini ditunjukkan dengan nilai rhitung pada masing-masing item lebih besar dari rtabel (0,3) artinya seluruh butir pernyataan variabel *turnover intention* (Y) dinyatakan valid.

The results of the reliability test recapitulation of the variable job satisfaction (0.938), organizational commitment (0.891), and turnover intention (0.910) show that the reliability value obtained is greater than the critical 0.6 for each variable, meaning that the measuring instrument used is reliable so that it can be concluded that the measurement tools used to measure the variables of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intention have provided consistent results.

Classic assumption test

1. Normality Test

Based on the results of the one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it shows that the study is normally distributed with a significance value of 0.200, meaning that the significance value is greater than 0.05. Normality testing is carried out using a histogram chart and using the normal P-Plot.

2. Multicollinearity Test

Based on the SPSS 26 test, it can be seen that the VIF value of each job satisfaction and organizational commitment as $1.826 < 5$ and the tolerance value is $0.548 > 0.05$ so that it can be concluded that in the regression model for the variables job satisfaction and organizational commitment there are no multicollinearity symptoms.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the scatterplot graph heteroscedasticity test show that the points spread randomly and are spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. This means that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model so that the regression model is feasible to use.

II. RESULTS

Employee characteristics

Table 2. Recapitulation of Employee Characteristics of CV Cahaya Kapasindo Employees

No	Characteristics	Description	Number (person)	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Female	114	91,9
2	Age	21 – 30 years old	84	68,0
2	Education	Junior high school	43	34,7
3	Long of work	1 - 2 years	34	27,4
4	Division	Sewing	49	39,5
5	Salary	1-2 million IDR	95	75,8
6	Compensation	1-2 million IDR	67	54,0

Source: Data primer diolah, 2022

Employee Response

Based on the results of distributing questionnaires on the job satisfaction variable (X1), it can be seen that the average value of employee responses to the job satisfaction variable of 2.26 is included in the dissatisfied category. The highest average of 2.65 with a neutral category is obtained on the co-worker indicator. The lowest average of 1.77 with the dissatisfied category is obtained on the promotion opportunity indicator. Companies can increase job satisfaction by providing promotional opportunities to employees as a form of appreciation. Good promotion is carried out through performance appraisal by applying a combination of experience and skills so that the employee to be promoted is the right person for the position and can provide maximum results, (Hermawan, 2020).

Employee responses to the organizational commitment variable (X2) can be seen that the average value of 2.52 is included in the low category. The highest average is 2.73 on the continuance commitment indicator, while the lowest is 2.38 on the normative commitment indicator. Organizational commitment can be increased by companies through rewarding the loyalty of employees who have served tenure. Awards are not always in financial form but can also be in non-financial forms in the form of commendations, certificates, trophies, vandels, badges, stars, honors, promotions, awarding higher positions, and promotions to lead an area, (Rivai & Sagala, 2014).

Employee responses to the turnover intention indicator obtain an average value of 3.93 which is included in the high category. The lowest average is 3.85 on the thought indicator to quit, while the highest average is 4.00 on the desire to find another job. Companies can reduce turnover intention by starting to plan a career management program based on performance appraisal.

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

Table 3. Regression Coefficient And Significance Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	40.420	1.411		28.644	.000
Kepuasan Kerja	-.239	.043	-.457	-5.590	.000
Komitmen Organisasional	-.369	.084	-.359	-4.396	.000

a. Dependent Variable: *Turnover Intention*

Sumber: Output pengolahan data dengan SPSS 26, 2022

The form of the equation in this study was calculated using multiple linear regression analysis. Based on Table 3, a regression equation is obtained with the estimated model as follows:

$$Y = 40,420 - 0,239X_1 - 0,369X_2 + e$$

Based on this equation, it can be concluded that a constant of 40.420 indicates that if the X variable does not change or is constant, Turnover Intention (Y) is positive. The regression coefficient of job satisfaction (X1) is -0.239 with a negative value and the regression coefficient of organizational commitment (X2) is -0.369 with a negative value. This means that an increase in the values of the job satisfaction variable (X1) and the organizational commitment variable (X2) will be followed by a decrease in the value of the turnover intention variable (Y).

Table 4. Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.747 ^a	.558	.551	3.37456

a. Predictors: (Constant), organizational commitment, job satisfaction

Sources: Output data process (SPSS 26), 2022

The coefficient of determination in Table 4 shows that the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment to turnover intention shows the number 0.747 which means it has a strong relationship. This shows that the higher the job satisfaction and organizational commitment, the lower the employee turnover intention of CV Cahaya Kapasindo. The percentage contribution to the influence of job satisfaction and organizational commitment variables on turnover intention is indicated by R Square of 0.558 or 55.8% while the remaining 44.2% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model, namely individual characteristics, work environment, (Mobley, 2011); work stress, (Tjahjono et al., 2017); organizational attachment, dan company culture, (Ridlo, 2012).

Tabel 5. Output F-test

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1738.576	2	869.288	76.336	.000 ^b
Residual	1377.908	121	11.388		
Total	3116.484	123			

a. Dependent Variable: *Turnover Intention*

b. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction, and organizational commitment

Sources: Output data process (SPSS 26), 2022

The first hypothesis in this study is that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant simultaneous effect on turnover intention. In Table 5 it can be seen that the significance value for the effect of job satisfaction (X1) and organizational commitment (X2) on turnover intention (Y) is 0.000 < 0.05 and F count 76.336 > F table value 3.08. This proves that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This means that there is a significant effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention.

Table 6. The Recapitulation of Partial Test

No.	Variabel	T _{tets}	Sig.	Description
1.	Job satisfaction	-5.590	0.000	There are negative and significant effect
2.	Organisational commitment	-4.396	0.000	There are negative and significant effect

Sumber: Output data processed (SPSS 26), 2022

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

The second hypothesis in this study is that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Based on Table 6 it can be seen that the variable job satisfaction obtains a $-t_{test}$ value of -5.590 and a $-t_{table}$ value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $124-2-1 = 121$ of -1.980 means $-t_{test} < -t_{table}$ ($-5.590 < -1.980$). So that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, meaning that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

The third hypothesis in this study is that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Based on Table 6 it can be seen that the organizational commitment variable obtains a $-t_{count}$ value of -4.396 and a $-t_{table}$ value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $124-2-1 = 121$ of -1.980 means $-t_{test} < -t_{table}$ ($-4.396 < -1.980$) so that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, meaning that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention..

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Turnover Intention

Based on the results of the data analysis performed, job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant effect simultaneously on turnover intention. In this study, increased job satisfaction and organizational commitment will reduce the level of turnover intention in companies, so that companies with career management can reduce turnover intention through performance appraisal. Performance appraisal is useful for helping employees improve their abilities and evaluate what has been done so far. Without job evaluation, employees can feel demotivated because their performance does not get an appraisal from their superiors. (Wulandari, 2020). Benefits of job evaluation as the fairest way to determine awards or rewards for achievements that have been achieved by employees, (Azizah, 2021). It is hoped that with a standardized performance appraisal, it can provide a sense of justice so that employees feel valued and ultimately there is no desire to leave the company. This is in line with research entitled "The Effect Of Job Satisfaction And Organizational Commitment On Turnover Intention At Beta Berlian Manado", the results of the study show that job satisfaction and organizational commitment simultaneously have a significant effect on turnover intention, (Waworuntu et al., 2022). Another study entitled "The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Turnover Intention" shows the results of job satisfaction and organizational commitment simultaneously have a significant effect on turnover intention, the findings of this study show the importance of job satisfaction and organizational commitment to Turnover Intention. Therefore, efforts are needed to increase job satisfaction and greater organizational commitment together. This effort can be done by increasing each variable that has the potential to affect Turnover Intention, especially job satisfaction and organizational commitment, (Ekhsan, 2019). Another study entitled "Revisiting the impact of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on nurse turnover intention: An individual differences analysis" shows that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant effect simultaneously on turnover intention, (Gieter et al., 2011).

The Effect of Job Satisfaction to *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of the data analysis performed, job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. In this study, increased job satisfaction will reduce the level of turnover intention in the company, so that the company can increase job satisfaction by providing promotion opportunities to employees as a form of appreciation. Good promotion is carried out through performance appraisal by applying a combination of experience and skills so that the employee to be promoted is the right person for the position and can provide maximum results, (Hermawan, 2020). This is in line with the research entitled "The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention and Its Impact on Employee Performance", the results of the study show that employee job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on employee turnover intention, where high employee job satisfaction will affect employee performance improvement. If employee job satisfaction is fulfilled, it will reduce the level of Employee Turnover Intention which will have an impact on increasing employee performance, (Rismayanti et al., 2018). Subsequent research entitled "Fear of COVID-19 and Its Impact on Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention Among Egyptian Physicians" which states that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, (Abd-Ellatif et al., 2021). Another study entitled "Effects of professional identity on turnover intention in China's hotel employees: The mediating role of employee engagement and job satisfaction" shows that job satisfaction has a negative and partially significant effect on turnover intention, (Wang et al., 2020).

The Effect of commitment Organizational to *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of the data analysis performed, organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. In this study, increased organizational commitment will reduce the level of turnover intention in the company, so that the company can increase organizational commitment through rewarding the loyalty of employees who have served tenure. Awards are not always in financial form but can also be in non-financial forms in the form of commendations, certificates, trophies, vandel, badges, stars, honors, promotions, awarding higher positions, and promotions to lead an area, (Rivai dan Sagala, 2014). As is the case for Civil Servants (PNS), there is an honorary title of honorary degree of satyalancana karya satya which is given to employees with 10, 20 and 30 years of service which can be used as a reference to be applied as a basis for awarding loyal employees in companies that has shown loyalty, dedication, skill, honesty and discipline and has worked continuously for at

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

least 10 years, 20 years or 30 years. This is in line with research entitled "The Effect of Job Insecurity and Organizational Commitment on Turnover Intention in Manufacturing Industry Employees", the results of the study show that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on employee turnover intention, which means that when organizational commitment to employees decreases, turnover employee intention will increase, (Handaru et al., 2021). Another study entitled "Organizational commitment and turnover intention among rural nurses in the Philippines: Implications for nursing management" states that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, (Labrague et al., 2018). Another study entitled "Related Factors of Turnover Intention Among Pediatric Nurses in Mainland China: A Structural Equation Modeling Analysis" says that organizational commitment factors have a direct negative effect on turnover intention, (Yang and Chen, 2020).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on job satisfaction and organizational commitment to operational employee turnover intention at CV Cahaya Kapisindo, Ciawi-Bogor, the following conclusions can be obtained:

1. Employee response to job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intention
 - a. Employees' assessment of job satisfaction is included in the dissatisfied category. The highest is on the co-worker indicator, and the lowest is on the promotion opportunity indicator.
 - b. Employees' assessment of organizational commitment is in the low category. The highest is on the indicator of continual commitment, and the lowest is on the normative indicator.
 - c. Employee assessment of turnover intention is included in the high category. highest on the indicator of the desire to find another job, and the lowest on the indicator of the thought of quitting.
2. Based on the results of simultaneous testing, it shows that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant influence on the turnover intention of operational employees at CV Cahaya Kapisindo.
3. Based on the partial test results between job satisfaction and organizational commitment to turnover intention:
 - a. Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention
 - b. Organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention

Hypothesis H1 is accepted which states that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant effect on turnover intention. Hypothesis H2 is accepted which states that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Hypothesis H3 is accepted which states that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

IV. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusions, there are several suggestions including:

1. Job satisfaction at CV Cahaya Kapisindo is classified as dissatisfied. Companies can increase job satisfaction by providing promotional opportunities to employees as a form of appreciation.
2. Organizational commitment at CV Cahaya Kapisindo is low. Organizational commitment can be increased by companies through rewarding employee loyalty based on years of service.
3. Turnover intention at CV Cahaya Kapisindo is included in the high category, but on average employees still work at the company. This can provide an opportunity for companies to evaluate job satisfaction and employee organizational commitment so that the current high turnover intention can be minimized so that there is no real turnover. Companies with career management can reduce turnover intention through performance appraisal.
4. For further research, other variables that can affect employee turnover intention can be added, including individual characteristics, work environment, work stress, attachment to the organization, and company culture.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abd-Ellatif, Eman E., Manal M. Anwar, Abobakr A. AlJifri, and Mervat M. El Dalatony. (2021). "Fear of COVID-19 and Its Impact on Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention Among Egyptian Physicians." *Safety and Health at Work* 12(4):490–95. doi: 10.1016/j.shaw.2021.07.007.
- 2) Azizah, Siti Nur. (2021). *Manajemen Kinerja*. 1st ed. edited by M. Nasrudin. Pekalongan: NEM.
- 3) Ekhsan, Muhamad. (2019). "The Influence Job Satisfaction And Organizational Commitment On Employee Turnover Intention." *Journal of Business, Management, and Accounting* 1(1):48–55.
- 4) Gieter, Sara De, Joeri Hofmans, and Roland Pepermans. (2011). "Revisiting the Impact of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Nurse Turnover Intention: An Individual Differences Analysis." *International Journal of Nursing Studies* 48(12):1562–69. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2011.06.007>.
- 5) Halimsetiono, Elita. (2014). "Peningkatan Komitmen Organisasi Untuk Menurunkan Angka Turnover Karyawan

Reduction Turnover Intention of Operational Employee: The Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment Approach

- Improvement of Organizational Commitment to Lower Employee Turnover.” *Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat Nasional* 8(8):339–45.
- 6) Handaru, Agung Wahyu, Nugie Fathur Rahman, and Widya Parimita. (2021). “Pengaruh Job Insecurity Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Turnover Intention Pada Karyawan Industri Manufaktur.” *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sains Indonesia* 12(1):15–39. doi: [tps://doi.org/10.21009/JRMSI.012.1.02](https://doi.org/10.21009/JRMSI.012.1.02).
 - 7) Hermawan, Sigit. (2020). *Buku Ajar Perilaku Rotasi Dan Promosi Jabatan?* 1st ed. edited by M. T. Maulana and R. R. Fauzan. Sidoarjo: UMSIDA Press.
 - 8) Indrasari, Meithiana. (2017). *Kepuasan Kerja Dan Kinerja Karyawan*. Yogyakarta: Indomedia Pustaka.
 - 9) Joarder, Mohd H. R., Mohmad Yazam Sharif, and Kawsar Ahmmed. (2011). “Mediating Role of Affective Commitment in HRM Practices and Turnover Intention Relationship: A Study in a Developing Context.” *Business and Economics Research Journal* 2(4):135–58.
 - 10) Kreitner, Robert, and Angelo Kinicki. (2014). *Perilaku Organisasi. Edisi 9. Buku 1*. 9th ed. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
 - 11) Labrague, Leodoro J., Denise M. McEnroe –. Petite, Konstantinos Tsaras, Jonas P. Cruz, Paolo C. Colet, and Donna S. Gloe. (2018). “Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention among Rural Nurses in the Philippines: Implications for Nursing Management.” *International Journal of Nursing Sciences* 5(4):403–8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.09.001>.
 - 12) Mobley, William H. (2011). *Pergantian Karyawan: Sebab, Akibat, Dan Pengendaliannya*. 1st ed. Jakarta: PT. Pustaka Binaman Pressindo.
 - 13) Mukminin, Amirul, Akhmad Habibi, Lantip Diat Prasajo, and Lia Yuliana. (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Dalam Pendidikan*. 1st ed. edited by B. A. P., N. Munthe, A. Tahalli, and N. Hariyati. Yogyakarta: UNY Press.
 - 14) Ningrum, Harini Fajar, Fitri Nasution, Purboyo, Dewi Sartika, Suriadi, Rachma Yuliana, Acai Sudirman, R. A. Nurlinda, Novi Marlana, Firina Lukitaningias, Zilawati, Aditya Wardhana, Pahri Siregar, and Ida Ayu Putu Widani Sugianingrat. (2021). *Pengantar Ilmu Manajemen (Sebuah Pendekatan Konseptual)*. 1st ed. edited by Hartini. Bandung: Media Sains Indonesia.
 - 15) Ratmawati, Dwi, Joko Suyono, and Anis Eliyana. (2020). “The Nightmare of Turnover Intention for Companies in Indonesia.” *Opcion* 36(91):871–88.
 - 16) Ridlo, Ilham Akhsanu. (2012). *Turn over (Literature Review) in Bahasa for Healthcare*. 1st ed. edited by IAR. Surabaya: Public Health Movement.
 - 17) Rismayanti, Revilia D., Moehammad Al Musadieq, and Edlyn Khurotul Aini. (2018). “Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Turnover Intention Serta Dampaknya Pada Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Pada Karyawan Tetap Pg Kebon Agung Malang).” *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis* 61(2):127–36.
 - 18) Rivai, Veithzal, and Ella Jauvani Sagala. (2014). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. 3rd ed. Depok: Rajawali Pers.
 - 19) Skousen, Fred., Earl K. Stice, and James D. Stice. (2009). *Akuntansi Keuangan Buku 2*. 1st ed. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
 - 20) Sutrisno, Edy. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. 8th ed. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
 - 21) Tjahjono, Heru Kurnianto, Sri Handari Wahyuningsih, Fauziyah, Agung Satiya Putrajat, Amelia Puspa Tamara, Andi Syaputra, Billy Andrian, Fatikha Rizdiana Dewi, Imelda, Lalu Supardin, Linggar Saputri, Musoli, Nurni Arrina Lestari, Rina Eka Widjayanti, Roisul Iksan, Roro Agung Prihatini, Septylyta Rahmita Putri, Siti Abdillah Nurhidayah, Suwarna Dianto, Tria Ratnasari, Uci Mariantika, and Yessi Novita Parimulya. 2017. *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia Dan Perilaku Organisasional*. 1st ed. edited by Heru Kurnianto Tjahjono. Yogyakarta: PPs UMY.
 - 22) Wang, Chaohui, Jiahui Xu, Tingting Christina Zhang, and Qinglian Melo Li. (2020). “Effects of Professional Identity on Turnover Intention in China’s Hotel Employees: The Mediating Role of Employee Engagement and Job Satisfaction.” *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management* 45:10–22. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2020.07.002>.
 - 23) Waworuntu, Dea Ursula, S. L. H. V. Joyce Lapijan, and Merinda H. C. Pandowo. (2022). “The Effect Of Job Satisfaction And Organizational Commitment On Turnover Intention At Beta Berlian Manado.” 10(3):643–51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v10i3.42301>.
 - 24) Wulandari, Fitri. (2020). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. 1st ed. Yogyakarta: Gerbang Media.
 - 25) Yang, Yuanyuan, and Jianjun Chen. (2020). “Related Factors of Turnover Intention Among Pediatric Nurses in Mainland China: A Structural Equation Modeling Analysis.” *Journal of Pediatric Nursing* 53:e217–23. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2020.04.018>.